

TITLE

RURAL CONSUMERS BEHAVIOR AND RURAL RETAILERS STRATEGY

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ABSTRACT

This Article examined the rural consumers' attitude towards Retailing Shops and retailers' strategy in selected Villages in Bengaluru Rural and Tumkur District areas. Research Methodology: A Survey method is used for primary data collection to quantify the opinions of the respondents selected for the study; their opinions are transformed into statistical inputs for further analysis. Secondary data was collected from books, journals, reports and articles. Buying pattern of the consumers and their relationship with the seller has the greater influence in retaining them. Findings: The study focused to understand the rural consumer' behavior towards the retailing shops there identified few factors based on these rural customers who visit the retail shops for purchase. To name the factors, convenient shopping: availability of all products, need convince, comfortable Shop procedure including credit facilities, affection towards the shop keeper, enduring service provided by the shop, word of mouth recommendation to show the attitude towards shop which have the power of generating reliability with the retail shop.

The retailer at rural are striving for securing place, putting their efforts with strategies. Some of the factors have strong influence to generate trustworthiness thus the retailers can consider strategically for retention of the customers which helps them to achieve business goal.

Conclusions: This study concluded that the Rural Consumers shows their attitudes in visiting the retail shops for purchasing. They do regularly visits the shops for buying the products needed for regular consumption; whom they believe offers low price, have good relationship, offer on credit, accepts exchange, lasting services and also looking into their comfortable and convenient. These behavioural aspects can be considered by the retailing shops as some important factors to attract the new customers and /or in retaining the existing ones thus builds strong customer relationship, loyal customer intern can create shop brand.

Suggestions: This study recommended the Rural Retailing shops to have a strategic plan to meet the expectations of the customers for their survival in the village and for further expansion.

KEY WORDS: Rural Consumer Behavior, Customer Relationship, retail shops; buying pattern; word of mouth encouragement; customer trustworthiness.

INTRODUCTION

Contribution from the rural to Indian economy is appreciable; retailing is one among the pillars of its economy and account noticeable percentage of its GDP. Retail developments in India and other major emerging economies would require not just innovations in practice but strong, ongoing efforts for theoretical renewal so that better explanatory frameworks are available for understanding marketing strategies and consumer behaviors in emerging settings. Small traditional stores provide competitive advantages to these small competitors (Ruby R. Dholakia, Nikhilesh Dholakia, Atish Chattopadhyay, 2018).

Retail stores in rural are unorganized in format and they are mostly of Kirana stores these are small neighborhood retail shops, Mom Pop shops which are of the kind that independently owned and run the business. Usually, small independent store across product categories is very common retail format in small townships and Village. Rural Consumers are depending on these shop and visits regularly for purchasing. Also, they are depending on Mandis and weekly bazaar for buying products occassionally.

Generally, rural customers are very money conscious in buying the products; they value the money and products. Today Rural population have increased their disposable income affected with various factors such as increased income, increased literacy level and controlled family size. Different categories of products that rural customers buy are food products, personal care products and household cleaning products, Agri – commodities. Though there are variety of retail shops like specialty store, convenient stores and marts for rural consumers in nearby towns, but the rural consumers are depending on unorganized retails shops to purchase their regular needy products or services for consumption for various reasons. Behavior of Rural Consumer is highly influenced by their own experience, form neighbor consumers and from own family members where family members have maximum influence (ASHISH KUMAR MISHRA, 2018). Moreover, to the shops they visit more number of times has feeling of faith,

in parallel, to the fact that, the sustainability of retailing shops in rural is solely depending on Rural Customers.

This study aims to understand the buying pattern of the Rural customers and to identify the other factors why the customers are reliable on retails shops, these factors foster the retailer shops to understand what the rural customers expects. Further these can be suggested for the rural retailers for strategic planning for Customer relationship building and management, to achieve business advantage.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

1. To understand the buying pattern of the rural customers.
2. To identify the factors that influences the rural customer for shop trustworthiness.
3. To suggest a strategic model for the retail shops at rural areas.

HYPOTHESIS

H1: Convenient shopping has significant impact on the customer trustworthiness towards retail shop.

H2: Convincing the need of the customers has significant impact on the customer dependability towards retail shop.

H3: Comfortable Shop procedure including credit facilities has positive impact on the customer dependability.

H4: Affection towards the shop owner has strong impact on the customer dependability on retail shop.

H5: Enduring services provide by the shop has significant impact on the customer trustworthiness towards retail shop.

H6: Word of Mouth encouragements by the fellow customers have an impact on the customer trustworthiness towards retail shop.

Theoretical concept on Consumer Behavior

Theory of consumer behavior in Economics describes how consumers allocate incomes among different goods and services to maximize their utility. Here consumer behavior is best understood with consumer preferences, budget constraints, and consumer choices. Theory of consumer behavior is surrounded with the fence of assumptions and the primary among these are: Consumers' wants and needs are unlimited and therefore cannot be fully satisfied. Consumers' limited purchasing power (budget) makes them to allocate the same in a way that maximize satisfaction of their wants and needs. Consumers' preferences are consistent over time and they are developed independently. Consumers have perfect knowledge i.e. they know exactly how much satisfaction they can gain from the consumption of a particular product. Price is the single decisive factor to measure the sacrifice involved in obtaining a product. Consumers are perfectly rational i.e. with their subjective preferences; they will always act in a planned manner to maximize their satisfaction.

The factors that influence the rural consumer while purchase of a product are socio cultural factors, group, family, status, sociability, economic and political factors (Leon Schiffman, Aron O'Cass, Angela Paladino, Jamie Carlson , 2014).

The major determinants drive the cognitive process of the consumer is arousal, behavior control, Emotions and critical thinking affects the abilities to make decision (Rajgopal, 2018).

Behavioural shift:

Behavioral sift is the process where the consumers come across with different preference, emotions, value and judgments and prevailing decisions, Social and cultural thinking also intervene in structuring the discernment and approach to achieve the utmost satisfaction. Trust is a collective behavior, which surfaces through the personality traits of the persons in the business group.

If a buyer relies on trust as a major factor for decision making, which in case not reciprocated, the company will suffer from substantial harm (Butler 1991), the consumer demonstrate two cognitive attribute during behavioral sift which are observation and self appraisal.

Reasoned action Theory

Since its inception this theory aids towards prediction of the Human actions in social (Fishbein and Ajzen (1975), also helps to predict how various factors impact a person's behaviour (Xiao, 2020). The theory posits that individuals' attitude and normative beliefs impact their behavioural intention which is a reliable predictor of their actual behaviour (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1970; Fishben & Ajzen, 1980). Reasoned action explained in various contexts and suggested that behavioural intention is a significant predictor of individual behavior such as knowledge sharing (Bock, Zmud, Kim, & Lee, 2005; Karnowski, Leonhard, & Kumpel, 2018). This indicates that reasoned action RA provides a reliable theoretical support to study customers' behavioural intention regarding visiting a store for shopping (Rehman, M., 2022).

Theory of Retailing Wheel Theory states that, the new retailer often enters the market with a low status, low profit margin, and low price store formats. Later they move to upmarket locations and stock premium products to differentiate themselves from imitators. Eventually they mature as high cost, high price retailers, vulnerable to new retailers who come up with some other novel retailing format /concept. This same retailer will in turn go through the same cycle of retail development.

Conceptual Frame work

The objective of the study is to identify the factors that influence the rural customer for development of trustworthiness, the customers are continued to visit the same shop and develop trust and belief based on the several factors like convenient shopping, convincing the

need of customers, comfortable shopping procedures including credit facilities, shoppers affection and word of mouth encouragements. The research conceptual frame work is as shown below:

LITERATURE REVIEW

Economic reforms in India have brought about major changes in the whole market environment. With these changes, rural marketing will become an important playground for marketers Kotler, Philip (1997).

Lutz Hildebrandt (1987) identified accessibility and diversity of retailers as important dimensions of retail satisfaction, which are affected by situational variables of the household.

The location of the household is shown to be a strong factor for (dis)satisfaction.

There are certain reasons behind the lacking of retailing in rural market but it can be moved or shifted towards paradigm shift by taking in consideration, traditional formats may included haats, mandies, established formats covering, kirana shops, convenience stores, cooperative

stores and emerging formats comprise exclusive retails outlet, Hyper market, rural oriented formats. (Gupta, C.P. and Chaturvedi Mitali, 2007; Malliswani, 2007; Prabha Laxmi, 2007).

Poonam Talwar, Sunita Sangwan and Kuldeep Sharma (2011) found that rural consumers prefer retail shopping since they are satisfied with the products offered and price, hence rural market has the wide opportunity for retailing. Further, considering of four p's viz product, price, place and promotion found that variety or quality of product, suitable prices, place of the retail store and promotional strategies have their great impact on the sales and retail growth.

Satya Narayanan S.R.(2015) in his article Customers' perception & satisfaction in organized retails sector in Rural India concluded Customers in rural area are concerned not only with merchandise, physical surrounding, personnel interaction but also with after sale services, this study suggested the retails stores to enhance product quality and store convenience.

Rural consumers are very conservative and apply utilitarian philosophy to a greater extent. Rural consumers prefer products with at most affordability, Rural villagers are self contended. Their values, life style, purpose of life, decision making process are all different rural consumers make their buying decisions only if there is dire need. (Ramanath H R and Dinakar G).

Rural marketing is important for developing a country's economy, manufacturers face many problems in marketing their product in rural areas because most of the rural consumers earn low incomes, have low levels of literacy, low levels of brand awareness, communication and transportation facilities (YUVARANI, 2013).

Dev Narayan Sarkar, Kaushik Kundu, Himadri Roy Chaudhuri (2016) found that to impact the purchase preferences of rural unorganized retailers: quality of supply and delivery, margins and profit, product demand, credit, brand reputation, social and personal recognition, sales force behaviour, seasonality and festivity, and company reputation. A marketer should

understand the factors influencing purchase behaviour while targeting rural retailers in developing markets.

MeeruJaswal and Shobhna Gupta (2017) in elucidated In India organized sector are developing reason is lack of time, increase of service class, but still rural and semi urban are still prefer to buy from Kirana store due to reliability, and boundness. Ease to buy and credit facilities provided by un-organised retail is still a major consideration while shopping”.

Retailers are taking notice, and some are looking for first-mover-advantage opportunities in rural areas where they see greater potential for growth when compared to saturated urban markets. (Rui Sousa, Carolina Horta, Ricardo Ribeiro, Elliot Rabinovich, 2020).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Exploratory method was followed in this study, the population comprises of the customers who visits the retailer shops of selected villages of Tumkur and Bangalore rural district of Karnataka. About 268 customers were participated for the data collection; survey method was used to collect the primary data. A questionnaire was prepared and used for data collection, Likert's five point scale measurement was used, response measured covered from strongly agree = 5 to strongly disagree =1, very satisfied = 5 to very dissatisfied=1, highly positive=5 to highly negative=1. The collected data was tabulated and analyzed using non parametric techniques. Hypothesis were set and tested, as per the resulted analysis, a study was concluded with suggestions.

Books, Journals, Articles were referred for secondary data collections.

DATA ANALYSIS AND REMARKS

Buying Pattern of the Rural Customer

The Rural Customer under the study have the habit of purchasing different category of products such as food products (34%) to list them staple food, oil, packed and baked foods, vegetables and fruits, soft drink and beverages. The personal care products (34%) included

tooth paste, bathing soap, shampoo, hair oil, face cream, talcum powder. House hold cleaning products (32%) included washing powder & detergents, dish wash soaps / powder, toilet and floor cleaner, cleaning tool items and related products. The pictorial representation of the same is shown in Figure 1. To infer, rural customers purchase all category of the consuming products regularly from the retail stores.

To come across where does the rural customer buy consuming products; analysis interpreted that, majority of the rural customers purchases the consuming products at retail shops in their village (45%), then at kirana shops (24%) near the home in villages, then at weekly bazaar (18%), very few go to supermarket in nearby Town (13%). The graphical representation is shown in Figure 2, choosing the shops for purchasing could have some influential factors to do so. The next question raised is how often do they buy the products, the response revealed that majority purchase on need base, whenever it is required (44%), then on weekly basis (27%) given that products arrive on weekly to the shops or visiting to weekly Bazaar, monthly basis (23%) and very few on daily (6%) which is presented in pictorial form as in Figure 3.

Customers visit same shops

In Rural villages, the customers are depending on some shops for purchasing the products, the factors identified from the existing research and while interacting with the Rural Customers which make them to visit the shops. The identified few factors are convenient shopping: availability of all products, need convince, comfortable shop procedure including credit facilities, affection towards the shop keeper, enduring service provided by the shop, word of mouth recommendation to show the attitude towards shop.

Coefficients results as in the Table 1 indicate significant positive correlation linking Customer dependability and identified six factors. The table also indicates that there is no

multicollinearity among the factors since all the VIF and tolerance values are less than 10 and more than 0.2 respectively.

The test the relationship between the overall shopping experience to be Trustworthiness to the Shop and identified factors hypothesis were set and analysed using Correlation and regression techniques.

H₀₁: Convenient shopping: availability of all products does not have significant impact on the customer trustworthiness on the same shop.

Analysis as shown in the Table 2 results the correlation is significant at 0.01 results at 0.206 and probability at .001 and affirm with R value at 0.206, which represents there is correlation to support Trustworthiness is explained by the variable convenient shopping: Availability of all products.

Further, regression analysis resulted at 0.001 and at $p < 0.05$ level of significance which indicates that, the regression model statistically significantly predicts the outcome variable. Hence the study rejects null hypotheses and accepts alternative hypothesis. This proves positive influence of convenient shopping- availability of all products on trustworthiness. By offering all the products to the customer have high power in generating Customer Trustworthiness.

H₀₂: Convincing the need of the customers does not have significant impact on the customer trustworthiness.

Correlation analysis done to find out the relationship between convenience and Trustworthiness as depicted in Table 3 resulted no significant association between convince the need and Customer Trustworthiness. R value resulted = 0.032, there exists some relationship.

Further, regression analysis resulted $p = .599$ which is > 0.05 level of significance which indicates that, the regression model statistically not significantly predicts the outcome

variable. Hence the study accepts null hypotheses. This proves no positive influence of convince the need on trustworthiness, means just convincing the product needs by the shop does not create the Customer Trustworthiness.

H₀₃: Comfortable Shop procedure including credit facilities does not have positive impact on the customer trustworthiness

From the analysis as shown in Table 4 the correlation is significant at 0 .01 level results at 0.295 and probability at 0.000 also affirm with R value at 0.295, which represents there is correlation to support Trustworthiness is explained by the variable Comfortable Shop procedure including credit facilities.

Further, regression analysis resulted at 0.000 and at $p < 0.05$ level of significance which indicates that, the regression model statistically significantly predicts the outcome variable. Hence the study rejects null hypotheses and accepts alternative hypothesis. This proves positive influence of Comfortable Shop procedure including credit facilities on trustworthiness; means comfortable procedure followed at shop have the power in creating Customer Trustworthiness.

H₀₄: Affection towards the shop owner does not have strong impact on the customer trustworthiness

Table 5 portray the correlation is significant at 0 .01 level results at 0.191 and probability at 0.002 also affirm with R value at 0.191, which represents there is correlation to support Trustworthiness is explained by the variable Affection towards the shop keeper.

Supplementing, regression analysis resulted at 0.002 and at $p < 0.05$ level of significance which indicates that, the regression model statistically significantly predicts the outcome variable. Hence, the study rejects null hypotheses and accepts alternative hypothesis. This proves positive influence of affection towards the shop keeper on trustworthiness; means the affection towards the shop keeper have the power in creating Customer Trustworthiness.

H₀₅: Enduring services provide by the shop do not have a significant impact on the customer trustworthiness.

The proven analysis as in Table 6 results no significant association between Enduring service provided by the shop and Customer Trustworthiness. R value resulted = 0.062, there exists some relationship.

Further, regression analysis resulted $p=0.310$ which is > 0.05 level of significance which indicates that, the regression model statistically not significantly predicts the outcome variable. Hence the study accepts null hypotheses. This proves no positive influence of Enduring service provided by the shop on trustworthiness, means just providing the enduring services to the customer does not create Trustworthiness.

H₀₆: Word of Mouth encouragement by the fellow customers does not have impact on the customer trustworthiness.

Analysis shows the correlation is significant at 0.01 level results at 0.312 and probability at 0.000 also affirm with R value at 0.312, which represents there is correlation to support Trustworthiness is explained by the variable Word of Mouth recommendation to show the attitude towards shop.

Supplementing, regression analysis resulted at 0.000 and at $p < 0.05$ level of significance which indicates that, the regression model statistically significantly predicts the outcome variable. Hence, the study rejects null hypotheses and accepts alternative hypothesis. This proves positive influence of Word of Mouth (WOM) recommendation to show the attitude towards shop on trustworthiness means WOM recommendation have the power in building Customer Trustworthiness. The resulted analysis is shown in Table 7.

This study found that, there exists relationship between customer trustworthiness and six identified factors, out of six factors, four have proved hypothetically that have significant impact on the customer trustworthiness.

SUGGESTIONS

The retails can positively develop trustworthiness of the rural customer by way of offering all category consuming products listed food products, staple food and oil, packed and baked foods, vegetables and fruits, soft drink and beverages. The personal care products included tooth paste & bathing soap, shampoo, hair oil, face cream, talcum powder. House hold cleaning products included washing powder & detergents , dish wash soaps / powder, toilet and floor cleaner, cleaning tool items so make the shopping convenient, following comfortable shopping procedure. The affection towards the shop vendor and informal Word of Mouth recommendations of the fellow customers can show trustworthy attitude towards the shop. The contra convincing the need of the products and with the assumption of continuing service old shop existing in the village for so many years does not have a positive impact in generating the customers' trustworthiness.

The Retails in the rural area can concentrate on the factors shows the favourably impact in generating the customers' trustworthiness, so the brand can be creating and can hold the customers for sustainability and to gain the competitive advantage.

The research model suggested for strategic implementation in retention of the Rural Customer by retailing shops is proposed herewith as Figure – 4.

CONCLUSIONS

The study titled “RETENTION STRATEGY OF RURAL CUSTOMERS IN RETAILING SHOPS “ was undertaken with the aim of proposing the strategic model to the retailing shops at rural areas. The main objectives of this study was to identify the facts that influence the rural customer for shop trustworthiness and to be acquainted with the strategies adopted by the retail shops in rural areas through the rural customers by understanding their pattern of purchase and overall shopping experience. It appears from this study that, six variables were identified viz convenient shopping, need convince, comfortable: shop procedure, affection

towards the shop keeper, enduring service provided by the shop, word of mouth recommendation to show the attitude towards shop; these contributes for customer trustworthiness. Few of these variables were understood form the existing research and other were from the participants' responses in the qualitative study. Some factors have positive impact on the customer Trustworthiness. The few factors can be considered as challenges by the Retailing shops in developing customer loyalty.

FURTHER RESEARCH SCOPE AND LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

In depth study was undertaken in the area of Rural Customer retention strategy for retailing shops, the factors identified are insufficient likewise identifying other factors can contribute in developing the precise strategic model. In conclusion, rural customers have the potential of purchasing the more quantity of products in smaller sizes and have ability in contributing more for the profit. Developing loyalty in Rural Customers is an interesting area and can be extended for sustainability of retail shops to gain competitive advantage, further several studies can be conducted to propose the new models and strategic suggestions.

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LIST OF TABLES

Table1: Coefficient result on co-linearity linking Trustworthiness and other factors

Coefficients^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Co linearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	1.636	.503		3.250	.001		
	Convenient shopping : Availability of all products	.508	.054	.558	9.350	.000	.695	1.439
	Convince the need	.086	.057	.082	1.506	.133	.831	1.203
	Comfortable :Shop procedure followed including credit facilities	.288	.058	.331	4.959	.000	.556	1.799
	Affection towards the shop keeper	.122	.045	.158	2.708	.007	.732	1.367
	Enduring service provided by the shop	-.001	.063	-.001	-.010	.992	.870	1.149
	Word of mouth recommendation to show the attitude towards shop	-.322	.051	-.361	-6.360	.000	.767	1.303

a. Dependent Variable: Trustworthiness

Table 2: Correlation and Regression Analysis –Convenient shopping versus Trustworthiness

Correlations			
		Convenient shopping : Availability of all products	Trustworthiness
Convenient shopping : Availability of all products	Pearson Correlation	1	.206**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001
	N	268	268
Trustworthiness	Pearson Correlation	.206**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	
	N	268	268

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Regression Analysis.

Model Summary^b										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.206 ^a	.042	.039	1.087	.042	11.785	1	266	.001	.115
a. Predictors: (Constant), Convenient shopping : Availability of all products										
b. Dependent Variable: Trustworthiness										

ANOVA^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	13.934	1	13.934	11.785	.001 ^b
	Residual	314.495	266	1.182		
	Total	328.429	267			
a. Dependent Variable: Trustworthiness						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Convenient shopping : Availability of all products						

Table 3: Correlation and Regression Analysis –Convince the need versus Trustworthiness

Correlations			
		Convince the need	Trustworthiness
Convince the need	Pearson Correlation	1	-.032
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.599
	N	268	268
Trustworthiness	Pearson Correlation	-.032	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.599	
	N	268	268

Model Summary^b										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.032 ^a	.001	-.003	1.111	.001	.278	1	266	.599	.108

a. Predictors: (Constant), Convince the need
 b. Dependent Variable: Trustworthiness

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.342	1	.342	.278	.599 ^b
	Residual	328.087	266	1.233		
	Total	328.429	267			
a. Dependent Variable: Trustworthiness						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Convince the need						

Table 4: Correlation and Regression Analysis –Comfortable shop versus Trustworthiness

Correlations			
		Comfortable: Shop procedure	Trustworthiness
Comfortable: Shop procedure	Pearson Correlation	1	.295 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	268	268
Trustworthiness	Pearson Correlation	.295 ^{**}	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	268	268
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

Model Summary ^b										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.295 ^a	.087	.084	1.062	.087	25.399	1	266	.000	.141
a. Predictors: (Constant), Comfortable :Shop procedure.										
b. Dependent Variable: Trustworthiness										

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	28.627	1	28.627	25.399	.000 ^b
	Residual	299.802	266	1.127		
	Total	328.429	267			
a. Dependent Variable: Trustworthiness						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Comfortable :Shop procedure.						

Table 5: Correlation and Regression Analysis – Affection towards the shop owner versus Trustworthiness

Correlations			
		Affection towards the shop keeper	Trustworthiness
Affection towards the shop keeper	Pearson Correlation	1	.191**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.002
	N	268	268
Trustworthiness	Pearson Correlation	.191**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	
	N	268	268

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Model Summary^b											
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson	
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change		
1	.191 ^a	.036	.033	1.091	.036	10.030	1	266	.002	.119	
a. Predictors: (Constant), Affection towards the shop keeper											
b. Dependent Variable: Trustworthiness											

ANOVA^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	11.934	1	11.934	10.030	.002 ^b
	Residual	316.495	266	1.190		
	Total	328.429	267			
a. Dependent Variable: Trustworthiness						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Affection towards the shop keeper						

Table 6 : Correlation and Regression Analysis – Enduring services provide by the shop versus Trustworthiness

Correlations			
		Enduring service provided by the shop	Trustworthiness
Enduring service provided by the shop	Pearson Correlation	1	.062
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.310
	N	268	268
Trustworthiness	Pearson Correlation	.062	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.310	
	N	268	268

Model Summary^b											
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson	
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change		
1	.062 ^a	.004	.000	1.109	.004	1.035	1	266	.310	.109	
a. Predictors: (Constant), Enduring service provided by the shop											
b. Dependent Variable: Trustworthiness											

ANOVA^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.272	1	1.272	1.035	.310 ^b
	Residual	327.157	266	1.230		
	Total	328.429	267			
a. Dependent Variable: Trustworthiness						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Enduring service provided by the shop						

Table 7 : Correlation and Regression Analysis – Word of Mouth Encouragement versus Trustworthiness

Correlations			
		Word of mouth recommendation to show the attitude towards shop	Trustworthiness
Word of mouth recommendation to show the attitude towards shop	Pearson Correlation	1	-.312 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	268	268
Trustworthiness	Pearson Correlation	-.312 ^{**}	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	268	268
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

Model Summary^b											
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson	
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change		
1	.312 ^a	.097	.094	1.056	.097	28.715	1	266	.000	.138	
a. Predictors: (Constant), Word of mouth recommendation to show the attitude towards shop											
b. Dependent Variable: Trustworthiness											

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	32.000	1	32.000	28.715	.000 ^b
	Residual	296.429	266	1.114		
	Total	328.429	267			
a. Dependent Variable: Trustworthiness						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Word of mouth recommendation to show the attitude towards shop						

LIST OF FIGURES ON BUYING PATTERN OF THE RURAL CUSTOMER:

Figure 4: Model for strategic implementation in retention of the Rural Customer by retailing shops

